

Environment and Its Influence

Flowering response of BPI-76 to 8-hour photoperiod

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We reexamined the effect of 8 h day-length on the flowering behavior of photoperiod-sensitive BPI-76 at 29-21 °C day/night temperature. Seedlings were sown in mid-Jul 1983 and grown under natural daylength. Plants aged 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, and 35 d were subjected to 8-h daylength for 5, 10, 15, and 20 d. After the treatments, plants grew to flowering under natural daylength.

Five-day-old seedlings treated for 5, 10, and 15 d had delayed heading of 1.3, 1.9, and 5.7 d compared with untreated plants (108.5 d after sowing). Twenty-day treatment caused plants to head significantly earlier—at 56.3 d after sowing.

Ten-day-old seedlings treated for 15

Number of days from sowing to heading of BPI-76 at an 8-h daylength for 5, 10, 15 and 20 d at various seedling ages, IRRI.

d and 15-d-old seedlings treated for 10 d headed 50.7 and 44.8 d earlier than untreated plants. Treating 10- to 35-d-old seedlings for 5 d had almost no effect (see figure).

The short-day treatment for 20 d

appeared to have the most distinct effect of shortening growth duration, and 15-d-old seedlings were most susceptible to 10-20 d short-day treatment. Our findings agreed with an earlier study by Vergara and Lilis. □

Effect of 24-hour photoperiod during booting on panicle development of four rices

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Photoperiod-sensitive varieties BPI-76, Wan-Xian 9, and Nong-Hu 6, and photoperiod-insensitive Lian-Tang-Zao were subjected to 10-h daylength after seeding in a 26°C glasshouse. At panicle initiation, one set of plants was exposed to 24-h photoperiod (10-h natural daylength plus 14-h artificial light at 1000 lux). A control set was continually exposed to 10-h daylength. Panicle development of 5 main shoots of dissected plants was examined by microscope every 2 d. The codes for describing floral stages in the apical bud ranged from 1 to 8.

The 24-h photoperiod delayed floral development 4 d after treatment in Nong-hu 6, but did not affect Wan-Xian 9 and

Panicle development of rice plants under 10-h and 24-h photoperiod, IRRI.

Exposure days	Panicle development stage							
	Lian-Tang-Zao		Wan-Xian 9		BPI-76		Nong-Hu 6	
	10-h	24-h	10-h	24-h	10-h	24-h	10-h	24-h
0	1.1	1.1	0.8	0.8	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.9
2	2.4	2.3	2.2	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	1.5
4	2.9	2.9	3.4	3.4	2.7	2.7	3.1	2.1
6	3.5	3.4	4.0	3.6	3.2	3.0	3.3	2.7
8	4.3	4.5	4.8	3.7	3.8	3.2	3.8	2.8
10	4.4	4.8	5.8	3.9	4.0	3.3	4.2	2.9
12	4.7	4.9	6.3	5.3	4.9	3.9	5.8	3.6
14	5.9	6.1	7.7	6.0	6.1	4.0	6.9	3.6
16	6.6	6.7	7.7	6.4	6.4	4.2	7.2	3.9
18	7.4	7.7	8.0 ^a	6.9	7.3	4.7	7.5	4.6
20	7.7	7.9	8.0	7.6	7.8	5.6	7.7	4.8

^a Stage 8 = just heading.

BPI-76. The inhibitory effect gradually increased with the number of exposure days. Twenty days after treatment, the floral stage of BPI-76 reached 7.8 in the control but only 5.6 in treated plants. Similar differences were obtained in Wan-Xian 9 and Nong-Hu 6. The inhibiting effect appeared to be stronger in the sinica variety Nong-Hu 6 than in the

other indica varieties. The treatment did not affect panicle development of Lian-Tang-Zao (see table).

The 24-h photoperiod prolonged the booting period and decreased the uniformity of panicle exertion in the photoperiod-sensitive varieties, indicating that short photoperiod during booting favors rapid, uniform panicle development. □